

EDITORIAL

Message from the Editor-in-Chief of
International Journal of Science Annals,
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**Background and
Aim of Study:**

Abstract

The Russian-Ukrainian war of 2022 has caused an ongoing humanitarian crisis that undermines stability both in Ukraine and around the world. The IJSA Editorial Office and the KRPOCH Publishing, located in Kharkiv (Ukraine), found themselves in extremely difficult conditions for the implementation of their scientific and publishing activities.

Results:

IJSA is a scientific, periodic, peer-reviewed Journal. The IJSA has been published and has been actively developing for 5 years. The Journal reviewed more than 300 manuscripts, 5 volumes were published. The IJSA has a clear and precise procedure for reviewing and selecting papers for publication. The IJSA Editorial Board includes the most authoritative scientists from 17 countries, 5 continents in the fields of Education, Psychology, and Medicine. The Journal is presented in more than 30 international scientometric databases, repositories and search engines, among them DOAJ, ERIH PLUS, COPE, MIAR, Crossref System, Google Scholar, ResearchGate, Zenodo, Scilit, etc. In 2018-2022 the KRPOCH Publishing and the IJSA initiated, co-organized, and sponsored the following academic projects: annual International Scientific and Practical Conferences "Psychological and Pedagogical Problems of Modern Specialist Formation" (PPPMSF), "Current Issues of Education and Science" (CIES), as well as the international competitions "Blockchain in the Digital Society" (ICBDS), "Mental Health in the Digital Society" (ICMHDS). These competitions were held among masters, graduate students, and young scientists.

Conclusions:

In this Editorial, I address the international academic community, universities and publishers who share our values and interests in supporting the Journal, as a sponsor or as an institutional partner of the IJSA.

Keywords:

journal, manuscripts, guidelines, peer review process, humanitarian crisis, institutional partner

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Dear Readers, Authors, and Publishers,

Russia's full-scale military invasion of Ukraine in February 2022 has led to a humanitarian crisis and created serious problems in many spheres of activity of the Ukrainian community.

The scientific community and research organizations have experienced all the hardships of the military situation. The Editorial Office of the International Journal of Science Annals (IJSA) and the IJSA Founder, Kharkiv Regional Public Organization "Culture of

Health” (KRPOCH), was located in the Ukrainian city of Kharkiv. The city was exposed to rocket, air and artillery attacks. The building of the IJSA Editorial Office and the KRPOCH Publishing was damaged by a rocket that exploded next to it, windows were shattered by shrapnel, and property was damaged.

KRPOCH employees were urgently evacuated to the west of Ukraine (Uzhgorod city), where they organized a volunteer center to provide socio-psychological and material assistance to internally displaced persons affected by Russian aggression. We have made every effort to implement previously planned national and international scientific projects: VII International Scientific and Practical Conference “Psychological and Pedagogical Problems of Modern Specialist Formation” (PPPMSF-2022), X International Scientific and Practical Conference “Current Issues of Education and Science” (CIES-2022), International Competition “Mental Health in the Digital Society” (ICMHDS-2022), as well as the preparation and publication of the IJSA, Vol. 5, 2022.

Months of missile strikes and the destruction of Ukraine’s critical infrastructure have caused massive disruptions and restrictions in power supply, the Internet and more.

These objective reasons, as well as the loss of computer equipment and printing equipment, made it almost impossible to implement some projects (PPPMSF-2022, ICMHDS-2022).

The IJSA Editorial Office had to be moved from Uzhhorod (Ukraine) to Vienna (Austria), where the implementation of the CIES-2022 project and the IJSA publication were temporarily continued.

In 2022, the IJSA Editorial Office received 32 manuscripts:

13 manuscripts (40.6%) were rejected during the preliminary evaluation process;

14 manuscripts (43.8%) were rejected during the peer review process;

5 manuscripts (15.6%) were accepted and published in this volume.

At the first stage, the reasons for rejection are the guidelines of the study have not been followed; the manuscript title is out of scope of the Journal, manuscript requirements have not been followed, the manuscript contains stylistic, spelling and syntax errors, plagiarism, etc.

At the second stage, the reasons for rejection are scientific relevance and practical importance are absent, methodological errors, there is no logic between the sections of the manuscript, etc.

We guarantee compliance the proper level of publication ethics, copyright protection at all stages of material review.

Therefore, the IJSA has a clear and precise procedure for reviewing and selecting papers for publication.

Our Journal solves the dilemma of quality and quantity of papers definitely in favor of quality (Melnyk & Pypenko, 2021).

The Journal should motivate young talented scientists to publish their manuscripts by providing them with

editorial support in the preparation of the manuscript and funding for its publication.

In 2022, as before, KRPOCH covered the costs from 80 to 100% for the publication of manuscripts accepted by the Journal.

KRPOCH is a non-profit organization that has received no public or private sponsorship funding for its publishing activities. Therefore, a strict editorial and review process, as well as limited financial resources, allow us to publish no more than 15% of the articles submitted to the Journal.

The subject of this Journal volume was devoted to topical issues of physical and mental health protection among schoolchildren, students, cadets in the conditions of martial law in Ukraine, international research in the field of hygiene, as well as research in the field of oncology and accompanying these persons.

The Journal is presented in more than 30 international scientometric databases, repositories and search engines, among them: Le Centre International de l’ISSN, ROAD (France); Crossref System, Google Scholar, GitHub, OAJI (USA); DOAJ (Sweden); OpenAIRE, ERIH PLUS (Norway); EndNote Click (Great Britain); COPE, Jisc (United Kingdom); BASE, ResearchGate (Germany); Zenodo; Scilit (Switzerland); MIAR (Spain); OUCI (Ukraine), etc.

I express my deep gratitude to all the IJSA Reviewers, as well as to the IJSA Editorial Board Members, for their work and moral support of our activities in this difficult time for us.

I also express my solidarity with leading publications such as Nature and Science (McNutt & Hildebrand, 2022), which have condemned Russia’s military aggression against Ukraine in editorials, as well as Elsevier, which took the initiative to provide financial support to Ukrainian researchers in its periodicals.

We hope that the international scientific community will render real help in rebuilding science and research infrastructure in Ukraine, an important component of which is the publishing activity of scientific periodicals.

We are currently looking for institutional partners among international academic organizations and publishing houses in order to restore and develop the IJSA.

Conclusions

The Russian-Ukrainian war of 2022 is an ongoing humanitarian crisis that is disrupting stability both in Ukraine and around the world.

This war has resulted in many deaths, severe damage to critical infrastructure and activities of the Ukrainian community. KRPOCH scientific and publishing activity has appeared in extremely difficult conditions. In essence, the question became about the survival of the IJSA.

In this Editorial, I address the international academic community, universities and publishers who share our values and interests in supporting the Journal, as a sponsor or as an institutional partner of the IJSA.

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The electronic version of this article is complete. It can be found online in the IJSA Archive <https://ijasa.culturehealth.org/en/arhiv>

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